

Solid Waste Management (A Need of The Time) The Spirit of Developed India

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Abstract:

In today's modern era, due to the rapidly increasing population, urbanization, and changing lifestyle, the amount of waste is increasing day by day. The disposable materials generated from human daily activities are called waste. This includes household waste, plastic, industrial waste, and hazardous medical waste. Nature gives us everything, but what do we give to nature? Only waste! Today, waste is not just a problem of a city or a country; it has become a serious global issue. In earlier times, waste was mainly biodegradable and decomposed naturally, but in today's era of plastic and technology, the generated waste does not decompose even when buried in the ground for thousands of years. To keep our Earth beautiful and clean, it is the duty of every citizen to understand the nature of waste and dispose of it properly. By implementing the concept of 'From Waste to Sustainable,' we can transform this problem into an opportunity.

Keywords: Reuse, Awareness, Waste-free City, Waste Segregation

Research Methodology:

This research method is based on secondary data. For this study, information was obtained from magazines, newspapers, research papers, articles, books, web references, and many other sources.

Waste refers to a substance that has become useless after use and is discarded. It includes household, industrial, agricultural waste, paper, plastic, glass, pieces of metal, leftover food, leaves, etc.

The two main types of waste are:

- 1) Solid Waste:** Solid waste refers to material in solid form that has become useless after use and is discarded. This waste is generated from households, markets, industries, and agriculture.
- 2) Liquid Waste:** Liquid waste refers to material in liquid form that has become useless after use and is discarded. This waste is generated from homes, industries, hospitals, or agriculture.

Main aspects of Solid Waste Management:

- 1) Waste classification:** Separating wet waste, dry waste, and hazardous waste.
- 2) Waste collection:** Waste collection means gathering unwanted waste and sending it to the appropriate place.
- 3) Waste transportation:** Transporting the collected waste to a suitable place for further processing is termed waste transportation.
- 4) Waste processing:** The process applied to the collected waste to make it useful or safe is called waste processing.
- 5) Safe Disposal of Garbage:** Safe disposal of garbage means throwing garbage in a safe place while ensuring that it does not harm the environment.
- 6) Reuse and Remanufacturing:** Reuse means using an item directly again, and remanufacturing means processing an item to make a new item.

How did lack of proper planning choke cities like Mumbai, Pune, and Shrigonda with garbage? Let's briefly see:

- 1) **Mumbai City:** Garbage in Mumbai city is a big and complex problem. Every day, around 6,500 to 98 tons of solid waste is generated in Mumbai, and disposing of it is a major challenge for the Brihanmumbai Municipal Corporation. This garbage is mainly dumped in Devnar and Kanjur Marg dumping grounds, which leads to problems like leaching diseases and groundwater pollution. Most of this garbage is domestic waste, but significant waste also comes from restaurants, markets, and industrial areas. Biodegradable waste is composted, and non-biodegradable waste is sent to recycling centers. If the garbage is not managed properly, it leads to pollution and health problem.
- 2) **Pune City:** In Pune city, the increasing population, industrial development, and urbanization have significantly increased the amount of waste. The management of this waste is primarily handled by the Pune Municipal Corporation. Approximately 2011 to 2200 tons of solid waste is generated daily in Pune, and according to some reports, this amount has recently increased to 2300 - 2400 tons per day.
 - 1) Among this, **Wet waste: about 950-1000 tons Dry waste: about 1200-1400 tons**
 - a. In the city, major projects are being implemented for producing compost fertilizer from wet waste and processing garden waste. With the collection and segregation of waste under the Swachh Bharat initiative, more than 3,000 women workers collect wet and dry waste from over six lakh households. Problems like unauthorized dumping of waste, accumulation of garbage in some areas, and mixed waste occur.
 - 2) **Shrigonda City:** There is significant irregularity in the solid waste management by the Shrigonda Municipal Council, and since new waste is being dumped on old waste,

serious health problems have arisen in the city. In response, the Sambhaji Brigade has expressed strong dissatisfaction and has indicated the possibility of protesting on this issue.

About ten tons of waste are collected in the city daily, but there appears to be a major deficiency in its management. As a result of accumulated old waste, there is a foul smell and piles of garbage in the city.

Some time ago, a fire at the solid waste project worsened the health problems. The Municipal Council spends approximately three crore rupees annually on solid waste management.

Problems faced while managing waste:

- 1) **Increasing population and high amount of waste:** In cities like Mumbai, Pune, and Shrigonda, the population is very high, so a lot of waste is generated daily. It becomes difficult to collect such a large amount of waste and dispose of it.
- 2) **Lack of space:** In big cities like Mumbai, Pune, and Shrigonda, open spaces are very limited, so there is not enough space to dump or process waste, which leads to accumulation and makes maintaining cleanliness difficult.
- 3) **Lack of public awareness:** In cities, some people are not aware of the importance of cleanliness, so they throw waste on the streets or do not separate wet and dry waste, which makes waste management difficult.
- 4) **Increasing amount of plastic waste:** The use of plastic has increased a lot in cities, so more plastic waste is generated. Plastic does not decompose quickly, making waste management difficult.
- 5) **Lack of waste segregation:** Many people do not separate wet and dry waste, so all the waste gets mixed together, making it difficult to process, which causes problems in waste management.
- 6) **Transportation and management difficulties:** There is a lot of traffic on the

roads, so waste collection vehicles find it difficult to work on time. As a result, waste is not collected on time, and the problem of waste in the city increases.

How did the city of Indore plan to become a garbage-free city? Let's take a brief look:

Indore (Madhya Pradesh) has been declared the cleanest city in India for eight consecutive years (up to 2024). This success is due to 100% door-to-door waste collection and categorization into six types. The administration focused on processing and recycling, which made the city garbage-free.

1) 100% wet and dry waste segregation:

Citizens are required to separate household waste into six different types, namely dry, wet, hazardous, plastic, etc.

2) Door-to-door waste collection: More than six hundred GPS-enabled vehicles collect segregated waste from every house and commercial establishment daily.

3) Penalty for not segregating waste: If wet and dry waste is found mixed, it is not accepted by the collection vehicles, and a fine is imposed.

4) Waste processing: The collected waste is processed instead of being dumped directly at dumping grounds. The city has a daily waste processing capacity of one thousand metric tons.

5) Bio-CNG Plant: Bio-CNG is produced from wet waste, which is used to run city buses. This generates revenue from waste (waste to wealth).

6) Revival of Rivers: To prevent the canals and Saraswati rivers flowing through the city from becoming clogged, 1,070 or more drains were directly connected.

7) Public Participation: Awareness among citizens was created through Swachhata Doots and local NGOs.

To reduce waste, we should do the following:

1. Take a cloth bag with you when going to the market.
2. Reuse old items instead of throwing them away.
3. Purchase items with less packaging and avoid buying more than necessary.
4. Reduce the use of paper.
5. Prepare compost from wet waste and use it in gardening.
6. Do not throw waste on the street or into the drain; dispose of it in a dustbin or as per municipal rules.

Conclusion:

From all the above information, it is evident that waste management is very important because it keeps the city clean, prevents diseases, and also protects the environment. Waste is not only the responsibility of the administration but also the duty of every citizen. Only if we all act responsibly and properly manage waste can we protect natural beauty and maintain the balance of nature. If citizens participate, awareness is raised, and modern technology is used, the city remains clean and healthy.

“Do not throw garbage anywhere on the road, It stains our own culture

Waste management is our responsibility, Only then will India be great.”

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